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ABSTRACT

The present study was conducted to assess the preference of different sections of society for the online shopping of electronics appliances, domestic goods, garments and footwear. The study included comprehensive analysis of 200 respondents (50 each under salaried people, businessmen, farmers and students category) with wide range of demographic characteristics (age, education and family size). Results revealed that ~58% salaried people, 18% farmers, 46% businessman and 68% of students prefer online shopping of garments for them-selves and their family. About ~74% of the salaried people prefer online purchase of sport shoes. Only ~10-14% of farmers prefer online purchase of sport and casual footwear. The proportion of respondents in respective category having preference for online purchase of mobile accessories was ~52, 6, 78 and 86%, respectively for salaried people, farmers, businessmen and students. Students had higher (~32% of total respondents in respective category) preference for online purchase of laptops, while for other categories it varied between nil and 14%. These results showed that students had higher preference for online shopping of garments, footwear, electronic appliances and gadgets, the farmers had the lowest, while the salaried people and businessmen class in-between.

KEYWORDS: Garments, footwear, mobile accessories, electronic gadgets, kitchen utensils.

1. INTRODUCTION

Online shopping is gaining ground among consumers in India (Handa and Gupta, 2008) as a convenient, less expensive and time saving process (Anitha, 2015). Online marketing is the direct linkage between the sellers and the consumers via internet, mobile communications and websites. Nonetheless, high product variety, lack of physical contact and social interaction has made online retailing as fascinating medium among people with different demographic characteristics (Anitha, 2015; Kanchan *et al.*, 2015; Agudo-Peregrina *et al.*, 2015). The 21st century has witnessed a dramatic shift in consumers shopping style which has so diversified that online shopping has increased worldwide (Johnson *et al.*, 2001). In India, online shopping has been preferred mostly by young educated people (Bhatt, 2014), particularly with age between 25-35 years (Anitha, 2015). Globally, the e-market (or e-commerce) which is currently a business of worth ~2.3 trillion dollar in 2016 has increased to ~4 trillion dollars by 2018 (John, 2018; e-marketer, 2016; e-marketer, 2018). Online shopping has been highly preferred by modern people because of their busy schedule and their unwillingness to spend time shopping (Rahman *et al.*, 2018). Studies showed that consumers' attitude towards online shopping is a major determinant affecting actual purchase behavior (Peterson *et al.*, 1997; Katawetawaraks and Wang, 2011). Online shopping satisfaction is considered to be influenced by merchandise attributes, state of mind of consumers, self-consciousness and payment security and privacy of credentials (Liu *et al.*, 2008; Mudambi and Schuff, 2010). Besides, the consumers trust and perceived benefits of online shopping are important that change the consumer's attitude towards online purchase (Hoque *et al.*, 2015). The concerns of price, product quality and resilience are important drivers of purchase decisions by the consumers in the developed countries, thought vary widely from the consumers in the developing countries (Hermes, 2000). Globally, the online shoppers are professional by education, younger in age, wealthier and had wired lifestyle (Bellman *et al.*, 1999). Generally, the potential online consumers use a two-stage process of screening products to identify a promising subset and then compare these products to make a purchase decision (Shergill and Chen, 2005). The risk associated with online shopping in the form of product return, money refunds and the security of transactions on the internet significantly influence

shopping at the final stage (Levin *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, to assess the attitude of different sections of society viz. salaried people, businessmen class, farming community and the students, the present study was conducted. The main objective of the present study was to investigate the preference of these sections of the society for online

shopping for their daily needs of garments, footwear, electronic gadgets, kitchen and home electrical appliances, and other articles (utensils, luggage bags, toys etc.).

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

Brief description about study

The present study was conducted in Punjab, north-western India to investigate the distribution of respondent's viz. salaried people, businessmen class, farming community and the students for their preference for online shopping. The information was gathered in a semi-structured interview schedule, which was pre-tested on 12 randomly selected respondents (3 respondents in each category). The questionnaire included information regarding demographic characteristics of the respondents and their preference for online shopping. For this survey, a total of 200 respondents; 50 in each category were randomly selected. The selection was made in such a way that each category includes respondents of different age group, education level and family size which are generally considered for making a conclusion on the distribution of population and assessing their preference for online shopping. In this study, the respondents of very young (age < 25 years) to medium to aged (age >45 years) were included. These respondents had small (1-4 family members) to large family sizes (> 8 family members). To discern the behavior of respondents towards online shopping, the survey included respondents which were illiterate as well as graduates or even post-graduates were also included.

Data compilation and interpretation

The data were compiled in Microsoft Excel Spreadsheets (MS Office, 2010). The data were analyzed for frequency distribution to categories respondents in each category based on their preference for online shopping. The preference of respondents was expressed as percent of total respondents for online shopping within each category.

Statistical analysis

The data were statistically analyzed by analysis of variance (ANOVA). The mean differences in each category were statistically analyzed using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). Mean difference significant at $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic characteristics of respondents

The respondents belonging to four categories viz. salaried, farmers, businessmen and students vary in age between <25 years to >45 years (Table 1). The proportion revealed that majority (~83.5%) of respondents were younger (<45 years) in age.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the respondents (n=200) selected for the assessment of online purchase scenario

Characteristics of respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Mean	Standard deviation
<u>Age (years)</u>				
<25	11	5.5	23.0	0.54
25-35	72	36.0	30.1	2.41
35-45	84	42.0	40.8	2.87
>45	33	16.5	56.8	3.92
<u>Family size (No. of members)</u>				
1-4	16	8.0	3.4	0.26

5-8	151	75.5	6.9	2.47
>8	33	16.5	8.4	3.19
<u>Educational qualification</u>				
Illiterate	05	2.5	-	-
Up to middle	24	12.0	-	-
Up to matric	73	36.5	-	-
Senior secondary	52	26.0	-	-
Graduation and above	46	23.0	-	-

Their proportion revealed that ~41.5% of total respondents included in the study were <35 years, while almost same (~42.0%) were between 35-45 years. Majority (~75.5%) of respondents included in the survey had between 5-8 family members, while ~8.0% of respondents had 1-4 family members. About 36.5% of respondents were matriculate, while ~23% were graduated. These results corroborate earlier research highlighting preference of youngsters with age between 25-35 years for online shopping in Tamil Nadu, India (Anitha, 2015). Young people had high interest in online shopping because they know about technology and e-shopping (Bhatt, 2014). Bellman *et al.*, (1999) reported that online shoppers are younger, more educated and wealthier and had wired lifestyle, and have more time constraint than non-internet (offline) shoppers.

Distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of garments

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution trend of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of garments adults and kids. Results revealed that ~58% salaried, 18% farmers, 46% businessman and 68% of students prefer online shopping of garments for them-selves and kids in their family. Among salaried people, 12 respondents (~24%) prefer purchase of garments for adults, 17 respondents (~34%) prefer online purchase of garments for kids, while 15 respondents (~30%) prefer purchase for both adults and kids. Among farmers, ~18% of total respondents in their respective category prefer online shopping of garments, with majority (~12%) purchase for kids.

Figure 1. Distribution of respondents based on their preference for the on-line purchase of garments. Mean values within a respondents class followed by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT)

Among businessmen category, ~46% of total respondents in respective category had preference for online purchase of garments. Of this category, ~30% prefer garments purchase for adults, while ~22% prefer purchase for both adults and kids. Among the four categories, the students had higher preference for online purchase. Among 34 students (~68% of total respondents in respective category), ~94% had preference for online purchase of garments for them-selves. The higher preference of salaried people and businessmen class, compared with the lowest by the farming community found support from the results of Bellman *et al.*, (1999) who reported that

online shoppers are more educated and wealthier and had wired lifestyle. Park and Cho (2012) reported that social network communities affect information seeking behavior and decision making for online apparel shopping.

Distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of footwear

The results revealed that ~74% of the salaried people prefer purchase of sport shoes, while ~52% prefer online purchase of casual footwear (Figure 2). Among businessmen category, ~62 and 56% prefer online purchase of sport and casual footwear, respectively.

Figure 2. Distribution of respondents based on their preference for the on-line purchase of footwear

Results revealed higher preference of online purchase of footwear by the students; ~78% prefer purchase of sport shoes, while ~60% prefer purchase of casual footwear. Only ~10-14% of farmers prefer online purchase of sport and casual footwear. Of the total salaried people who prefer online purchase of sport footwear, ~73% purchase for adults, while ~27% prefer for kids. Similar trend was observed for the purchase of sport and casual footwear by businessmen category. However, among students, majority had preference of purchase for them-selves. Nordin and Selke (2010) reported that there is inconsistency between consumers’ attitudes and behavior, due to the consumers’ overwhelming lack of knowledge about the sustainability concept.

Distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of electronic appliances

The distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of electronic appliances showed wide variation (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of respondents based on their preference for the online purchase of different electronic appliances

Type of electronic item	Salaried (n=50)	Farmers (n=50)	Businessman (n=50)	Students (n=50)
<u>Electronic gadgets</u>				
Mobile phones	47 ^c (94.0) [¶]	27 ^a (54.0)	43 ^b (86.0)	50 ^{cd} (100.0)
Mobile accessories	26 ^b (52.0)	3 ^a (6.0)	39 ^c (78.0)	43 ^c (86.0)

Tablets	10 ^b (20.0)	0 ^a (0.0)	11 ^b (22.0)	15 ^d (30.0)
Laptops	5 ^b (10.0)	0 ^a (0.0)	7 ^b (14.0)	16 ^c (32.0)
Computer accessories	32 ^b (64.0)	4 ^a (8.0)	29 ^b (58.0)	43 ^c (86.0)
Home appliances				
Press (Iron)	8 ^c (16.0)	1 ^a (2.0)	11 ^d (22.0)	3 ^b (6.0)
LED (TV)	14 ^c (28.0)	2 ^b (4.0)	18 ^c (36.0)	0 ^a (0.0)
LED bulbs	26 ^b (52.0)	3 ^a (6.0)	38 ^c (76.0)	5 ^a (10.0)
Fans/ACs	17 ^b (34.0)	1 ^a (2.0)	24 ^c (48.0)	0 ^a (0.0)
Kitchen appliances				
Hand blender	7 ^b (14.0)	1 ^a (2.0)	16 ^c (32.0)	1 ^a (2.0)
Chopper	5 ^b (10.0)	0 ^a (0.0)	19 ^c (38.0)	1 ^a (2.0)
Sandwich maker	4 ^c (8.0)	0 ^a (0.0)	7 ^d (14.0)	2 ^b (4.0)
Juicers	3 ^b (6.0)	0 ^a (0.0)	2 ^b (4.0)	0 ^a (0.0)

*Values in the parentheses indicate % of respondents in respective category

Mean values within a respondents class followed by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ by Duncans' Multiple Range Test (DMRT)

Among electronic gadgets, online purchase of mobile phones had been the most preferred item. Results revealed that ~94, 54, 86 and 100% of salaried people, farmers, businessmen and students in their respective category prefer online purchase of mobiles. The proportion of respondents in respective category having preference for online purchase of mobile accessories was ~52, 6, 78 and 86%, respectively for salaried people, farmers, businessmen and students. Students had higher (~32% of total respondents in respective category) preference for online purchase of laptops, while for other categories it varied between nil and 14%. Among home appliances, businessmen had higher preference (36% of total respondents) for online purchase of LED (TV), followed by salaried people (28% of total respondents). Similarly, the preference for online purchase of electric fans and ACs had been associated with businessmen and salaried people. For online purchase of different kitchen appliances, farmers and students had the little preference while the businessmen and salaried people had the highest preference. Alba *et al.*, (1997) recognized the importance of product and consumer differences in the success of the electronic marketplace.

Distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of kitchen utensils

The distribution of respondents based on their preference for online purchase of kitchen utensils and grocery revealed that businessmen class had the highest, while the students and farmers had the least preference (Table 3).

Table 3. Distribution of respondents based on their preference for the online purchase of crockery and utensils

Item	Salaried (n=50)	Farmers (n=50)	Businessman (n=50)	Students (n=50)
Crockery	12 ^b (24) [¶]	2 ^a (4)	11 ^b (22)	1 ^a (2)
Pressure cookers	17 ^b (34)	2 ^a (4)	19 ^b (38)	2 ^a (4)
Tiffin's	9 ^c (18)	1 ^a (2)	24 ^d (48)	3 ^b (6)
Water bottles	26 ^b (52)	3 ^a (6)	34 ^c (68)	26 ^b (52)

¶Values in the parentheses indicate % of respondents in respective category

Mean values within a respondents class followed by different letters are significantly different at $p < 0.05$ by Duncans' Multiple Range Test (DMRT)

The salaried people also had high preference for online purchase of these articles but were lower than the businessmen class. Among different kitchen utensils, the highest preference had been for the purchase of water bottles (52-68%). The respondents considered under salaried people and businessmen class showed 18 and 48% preference for online purchase of Tiffin's. Online shopping by the modern people help saving their time because of their unwillingness to spend much time for online shopping (Rahman *et al.*, 2018).

4. CONCLUSIONS

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The present study revealed that students had the higher preference for online shopping, compared with the other section of society. The salaried people and businessmen also had higher preference for online purchase of garments, footwear, electronics and kitchen appliances. Among electronic appliances, respondents preferred online shopping of electronic gadgets such as mobiles, LED-TV etc. The farmers had the lowest preference for online shopping.

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